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A STUDY ON DETECTING ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS REPORTING IN A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Background: An adverse drug reaction (ADR) is a reaction which is noxious and unintended and which occurs at dosages normally used in man for prophylaxis, diagnosis or therapy of disease or for the modification of physiological function. It is important to identify the risks for ADRs, hence forth the common drugs causing ADRs, their therapeutic class, demographic data of patients suffered from ADRs & concomitant medications used should be known. Also ADR specific data such as type of reaction, system affected and probable causes will be of great help to minimize the ADRs. To detect the ADRs through spontaneous reporting system in our tertiary care teaching hospital and analyzing them by using World Health Organization (WHO) assessment scales. Method: An prospective observational study was conducted based on ADRs reporting between 1st June 2017 to 31st May 2018 to the ADR reporting unit of the our hospital i.e., Pharmacovigilance cell. The ADRs reported by spontaneous reporting system were from patients attending outpatient department (OPD), inpatient department (IPD) and casualty department. Evaluation of the data was done for various parameters which included patient demographics, drug and reaction characteristics and outcome of the reactions. Assessment was also done for causality and severity. Result: Total 2639 ADRs were reported with in the period from 1st June 2017 to 31st May 2018. Antimicrobial agents (AMA) were the drug class most commonly involved and Non-Steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) were next to AMA. Cotrimoxazole a well-established agent was the individual drug most frequently reported in this study. Upon causality assessment, majority of the reports were rated as probable (55.89 %). Conclusion: The pattern of ADRs reported in our hospital is comparable with the results of other studies conducted in various hospital set up elsewhere. AMAs were causing maximum ADRs. This study provides a database of ADRs due to common drugs used in our hospital, which will help clinicians for optimum and safe use of these drugs. Hence strict vigilance is required for the use of these likely drugs and their safety assessment.

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INTRODUCTION

An adverse reaction is a reaction which is noxious and unintended and which occurs at dosages normally used in man for prophylaxis, diagnosis or therapy of disease or for the modification of physiological function. This definition is independent of the mechanism of the adverse reaction and includes allergies, idiosyncrasies, pharmacological and toxicological mechanisms and interactions between different drugs.¹ In the case of clinical trials injuries by overdosing, abuse/dependence and interactions with other medicinal products should also be considered adverse drug reactions.² Previous studies indicated that ADRs account for 5 % of all hospital admissions and occur in 10 – 20 % of hospitalized patients.³⁻⁶ Lazarou et al reported an overall incidence of serious and fatal ADRs of 6.7 % and 0.32 %, respectively, of hospitalized patients.⁷

ADRs may arise as a result of Immunological or non-immunological mechanisms.⁸ According to Rawlins & Thompson classification, ADRs are defined as type A, type B, type C and type D.⁹ A type A reaction is an over enhancement of the normal pharmacology of the medication, is predictable and is related to dosage. A type B reaction is unrelated to normal pharmacology, is unpredictable. Type C reactions include those associated with prolonged therapy example, analgesic nephropathy. Type D reactions consist of delayed reactions example, carcinogenesis and teratogenesis. The probability of causative agent is assessed by the ADR probability designed by Naranjo et al and classified as definitive, probable, possible and suspected.¹⁰ It is important to identify the risks for ADRs, hence forth the common drugs causing ADRs, their therapeutic class, demographic data of patients suffered from ADRs & concomitant medications used should be known. Also ADR specific data such as type of reaction, system affected and probable causes will be of great help to minimize the ADRs.¹¹

The present study aims to identify and characterize the pattern of ADRs due to commonly used drugs in tertiary care teaching hospital and analyse them on the basis of various parameters. This information may be useful in identifying and minimizing preventable ADRs, at the same time it may help clinicians to tackle with ADRs more efficiently.

METHODS

An observational, prospective study was performed in patients attending outpatient department (OPD), inpatient department (IPD) and casualty of our hospital from 1st June 2017 to 31st May 2018. Study was approved by the institutional ethics committee. All the suspected patients of ADR in the hospital were referred to respective physician and the diagnosis was made by physician. The data was recorded as per spontaneous ADR reporting system.¹²

The data was recorded as per ADR form obtained from Central Drugs Standard Control Organisation (CDSCO) website. The patient's initials, age, gender, type of ADR, history of disease, starting date of ADR, suspected drug causing ADR were noted. The causality assessment was done by using WHO causality scale and physician from respective department helped in this procedure. According to WHO terminology, ADR was recorded to be serious as per definition "Adverse event is serious when the patient outcome is death, life threatening, hospitalization, disability, congenital anomaly and required intervention to prevent permanent impairment or damage". We assessed the seriousness of ADRs according to this definition.¹³ The data was analyzed with simple statistical proportions.

RESULT:

A total of 2639 ADRs were reported in the span of period from 1st June 2017 to 31st May 2018. The year wise distribution of ADRs indicates that almost similar number of ADRs were reported in each year but in year June 2016 to May 2017 there was slight rise in the number of ADRs might be due to the epidemic of chicken guinea (Table 1).

Table 1 Year wise distribution of ADRs.

SL. NO.	Study Period	No. of ADRs
1.	1 st June 2014 to 31 st May 2015	665
2.	1 st June 2015 to 31 st May 2016	722
3.	1 st June 2016 to 31 st May 2017	648
4.	1 st June 2017 to 31 st May 2018	604
5.	TOTAL	2639

Out of total ADRs 1559 male suffered from ADRs while only 1080 females. Males affected more due to ADRs as compared to females. All were mostly in age group of 21 – 40 years (Table 2).

Table 2 Gender & Age wise distribution of ADRs.

Age groups in years	Males	Females	No. of ADRs	Percentage of ADRs
1 – 11	51	28	79	2.99
12 – 20	206	140	346	13.11
21 – 40	849	675	1524	57.74
41 – 60	393	200	593	22.47
>60	60	37	97	3.67
Total	1559	1080	2639	100

It was seen that most of the ADRs were reported from Medicine Department (32.66 %) and followed by other departments like Skin (23.98 %), Psychiatry (14.24 %), Obstetrics & gynecology (6.17 %), Chest and TB (5.79 %) etc. (Table 3).

Table 3 Department wise distribution of ADRs.

Department	No. of ADRs	Percentage of ADRs
General Medicine	862	32.66
Skin and cosmetology	633	23.98
Psychiatry	376	14.24
OBGY	163	6.17
Chest & TB	153	5.79
Orthopaedics	128	4.85
ENT	125	4.73
Other specializations	208	7.88
Total	2639	100

In this study, skin is the most commonly affected organ system (37.24 %). Gastrointestinal tract system (GIT) is involved in 32.51 % of ADRs. Other organ systems involved are central nervous system (CNS), autonomic nervous system (ANS) and respiratory system (RS) (Table 4). Wide varieties of side effects are observed. The most important were gastrointestinal such as dyspepsia, nausea, vomiting gastritis and cutaneous reactions such as fixed drug eruption, itching, urticaria, maculopapular rashes, vasculitis phototoxic reactions, erythema multiforme, toxic epidermal necrosis and Steven Johnson syndrome.

Table 4 Organ system affected basis distribution of ADRs.

System affected	No. of ADRs	Percentage of ADRs
Skin	983	37.24
GIT	858	32.51
CNS	456	17.27
ANS	92	3.48
RS	56	2.12
Hepatic	39	1.47
Others	156	5.91
Total	2639	100

The top 10 drugs causing ADRs in our study are shown in (Table 5). Cotrimoxazole (9.73 %) has found to be most commonly offending drug. Others were ampicillin (9.09 %), ibuprofen (6.21 %) rifampicin (3.29 %), azithromycin (2.95 %) and chloroquine (2.76 %) et., 34 ADRs were reported serious, as per WHO definition, out of which 2 were fatal. These were angioedema (13), Steven Johnson Syndrome (12), anaphylaxis (6), nephrotoxicity (2) and laryngospasm (1) (Table 6).

Table 5 Top 10 Drugs involved in causing ADRs.

Drug involved	No. of ADRs	Percentage of ADRs
Cotrimoxazole	257	9.73
Ampicillin	240	9.09
Ibuprofen	164	6.21
Rifampicin	87	3.29
Azithromycin	78	2.95
Chloroquine	73	2.76
Erythromycin	70	2.65
Ofloxacin	60	2.27
Metronidazole	59	2.23
Ciprofloxacin	57	2.15

Table 6 Seriousness wise distribution of ADRs with causing DRUGs.

SL. NO.	Seriousness of ADRs	No. of Serious ADRs	DRUGs involved	No. of ADRs
1.	Steven Johnson Syndrome	12	Ciprofloxacin	4
			Cotrimoxazole	2
			Cephalexin	1
			Ofloxacin	1
			Ibuprofen	1
			Diclofenac	1
			Paracetamol	1
			Nimesulide	1
2.	Anaphylaxis	06	Penicillin	3
			Ciprofloxacin	1
			Diclofenac	2
			Ciprofloxacin	1
3.	Angioedema	13	Chloroquine	1
			Ceftriaxone	1
			Paracetamol	3
			Diclofenac	5
			Ibuprofen	1
4.	Nephrotoxicity	02	Nimesulide	1
			Cefadroxil	1
			Gentamicin	1
5.	Laryngospasm	01	Penicillin	1

Note: * 1 ADR due to Ciprofloxacin and 1 ADR due to Penicillin were found to be fatal.

Upon causality assessment, majority of the reports were rated as probable (53.7 %). 999 possible and only 165 ADRs were classified as certain. Mild and moderate reactions accounted for 50.5 and 43.9 %, respectively (Table 7).

Table 7 Causality Assessment of ADRs.

SL. NO.	Causality Assessment of ADRs	No. of ADRs	Percentage of ADRs
1.	Certain	165	6.25
2.	Possible	999	37.85
3.	Probable	1475	53.7
	Total	2639	97.8

The routes of administration of drugs are depicted in (Table 8). Majority of ADRs were noted with oral route of administration (83.74 %). Drugs administered by parenteral route accounted for 8.14 % of ADRs, while 8.07 % of the drugs given topically caused ADR.

Table 8 Routes of Administration of Drugs wise distribution of ADRs.

SL. NO.	Routes of Administration of Drugs	No. of ADRs	Percentage of ADRs
1.	Oral	2210	83.74
2.	Parenteral	215	8.14
3.	Topical	213	8.07
	Total	2638	100

DISCUSSION

As seen from the data, ADR seem to be a common problem in patients getting drugs of all types. The distribution (yearly) indicates fairly uniform trend of occurrence of ADR in males. ADRs were common in 21 - 40 yrs age group. It is likely that this population is attending hospital more frequently and is a major population receiving drug therapy.

As predicted the bulk of ADR are reported from medicine department. It is a department that relies on drug therapy to the maximum. All the patients reported to skin department may be permanently attending skin OPD or may be referred from other departments. Psychopharmacological agents are being increasingly used and recent drugs are being tried. Data reveals a large number of ADR due to these agents.

Skin seems to be most common organ system affected followed by GIT. It is likely that patients being extra cautious about glaring ADR of skin have come rushing to hospital. People also may be worried about GIT problems and CNS symptoms due to drugs, nevertheless commonly used drugs like antimicrobials and analgesics cause ADR. It is seen that ADR may be related to any system.^{14, 15} Our data is comparable to study conducted by Linden et al. It concludes that Cotrimoxazole, fluoroquinolones and penicillins were the most common AMAs causing dermatomucosal ADRs.¹⁶

The causality assessment of 1475 ADR revealed that most of the ADRs belonged to “probable” followed by “possible” categories, similar to that reported Italian study.¹⁷ It is likely that physicians were adopting spontaneous reporting system and hence they sent to us the information mostly when they were themselves convinced about cause of ADR being drug.

The top ten drugs responsible for ADRs in our study are very commonly used drugs. It gives complete proof for the need of continuous ADR monitoring system in hospital. This is the first data from our hospital which was reported about ADR in patients of our hospital. In the top 10 drugs causing ADR, 9 are AMAs while 1 is NSAID. The top most drugs is a well-established one (Cotrimoxazole). All the drugs are well known agents leading to such large number of ADRs. It must be further analysed by intensive monitoring strategies regarding any medication errors, patient factors and underlying cause of these ADR. It is well known that oral route is commonest and hence ADR were also commonest with oral route.

Due to various reasons like absence of data base of drug prescription and limited manpower it was not possible to assess actual incidence of ADR to drugs as there was no denominator. This study suffers the main drawback of spontaneous reporting system i.e. underreporting. Despite the limitations and variations in the study, data obtained from this research will be helpful for clinicians regarding careful selection and limited use of AMAs and NSAIDs. This study reflects the need to carefully assess safety, monitoring, preventability and treatment of ADR of conventional drugs. It may a beginning of more serious efforts on part of physicians to report each and every ADR they come across while administering the drugs in a tertiary care hospital where patients are exposed to large spectra of drugs.¹⁸

CONCLUSION

From this study we concluded that the data of this study is very extensive and stretched over the period of 5 years. Many studies carried out in this respect but very few are compatible to the period of our study. The pattern of ADRs reported in our hospital is comparable with the results of studies conducted in hospital set up elsewhere. It provides a database of ADRs due to common drugs used in our hospital, which will help clinicians for optimum and safe use of these drugs. Hence strict Pharmacovigilance and clinical pharmacist role play is required for the use of these likely drugs and their safety assessment.

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